

RESEARCH OF MARKETING ACTIVITIES IN THE PRODUCTION ENTERPRISE "OR GOLDEN OIL" LLC

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Abstract. In this article, the production, processing and sale of consumer goods and food products, enterprise the main results of its activity are analyzed by its financial indicators and the balance sheet of the enterprise.

Keywords: enterprise, competition, independence, food products, market, sales, demand, supply.

ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ МАРКЕТИНГОВОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ ПРОИЗВОДСТВЕННОГО ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯ ООО «OR GOLDEN OIL»

Аннотация. В данной статье производство, переработка и реализация товаров народного потребления и продуктов питания, основные результаты деятельности предприятия анализируются по его финансовым показателям и балансу предприятия.

Ключевые слова: предприятие, конкуренция, самостоятельность, продовольственные товары, рынок, сбыт, спрос, предложение.

INTRODUCTION

Meeting the population's need for material goods has always been one of the most important life issues. This is undoubtedly due to population growth.

At this time, it is important to solve the issues of ensuring food security in our country, filling the markets with quality products, using every inch of fertile land effectively, increasing food production, and ensuring price stability in the markets.

The widespread use of marketing activities in enterprises of the Republic of Uzbekistan leads to the development of marketing science in our country. Currently, researching the consumer market, determining the needs of customers and adapting to them is becoming a common situation for every industry and trade organization. Thus, it is clear that the application of all the achievements of marketing will have a positive effect on the efficiency of enterprises and organizations.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Results (research results) The result of this article is to clarify the essence of introducing goods distribution and sales promotion activities in the production enterprise of "OR GOLDEN OIL" LLC under the conditions of economic liberalization, to justify its forms, and to develop recommendations for practice in this field.

RESULTS

It is proposed to consider the distribution of goods in food enterprises as a separate process due to the conditions of the market economy.

Ways to improve marketing activities and thereby achieve efficiency in a modern production enterprise are shown.

Issues of competitiveness in the modern economy are related to the level of independence of the country. It is known that the independence of any country depends on several elements:

- Political independence;
- Territorial immunity;
- Energy independence;
- Food independence.

In recent years, the issues of food independence and safety have occupied one of the main places in the world. In this regard, comprehensive programs for the development of food production have been created and are being implemented in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

As we all know, the sustainable food supply of society depends on the adequate production of basic food products. Such products include vegetable oil. Due to the role of vegetable oil in human life, the number of enterprises specializing in the production of this product is increasing in our country.

The largest enterprise specializing in the production of vegetable oil in the Samarkand region is "Kattakurgan oil-oil" open joint-stock company. At the same time, as a result of measures aimed at increasing competition in the market of oil products, many alternative production enterprises have started their activities in recent years. In our master's dissertation, the limited liability company "OR GOLDEN OIL" located in the city of Samarkand was used as an example.

"OR GOLDEN OIL" LLC production enterprise was established on January 21, 2004 under the "Damir" private production company.

Currently, more than 150 oil-oil, meat-milk, fruit-vegetable processing and other food industry enterprises are operating within the association. Production of more than a thousand types of products has been launched in them, vegetable oils, margarine, sugar, mineral water, confectionery, milk, meat and fruit and vegetable canned products are being prepared.

The main goal of the production enterprise "OR GOLDEN OIL" LLC is to provide the population of the Republic of Uzbekistan with jobs, to satisfy their needs for various types of products and services, as well as to get profit from entrepreneurship.

The main activity of the enterprise is production and sale of vegetable and animal fat, production, processing and sale of products related to vegetable and animal fat.

At the same time, the charter of "OR GOLDEN OIL" LLC production enterprise stipulates that it is possible to engage in a number of additional activities:

- production, processing and sale of consumer goods and food products;
- Production and sale of knitted products;
- Production and sale of processing of leather products;
- Production and sale of thirst-quenching drinks;
- Organization of wholesale and retail chavdo shops, catering establishments;
- Production and sale of construction products;
- Foreign economic activities, export and import of goods and services, etc.

In the charter of the society, it is indicated that it is possible to engage in more than 20 types of activities.

The following equipment is currently installed in the enterprise:

1. 10 tons per day technical seed processing equipment manufactured by the company "Demetra" of the Russian Federation, installed in 2003.

2. Xinjiang Qarluq International Trade Co., Ltd. of the People's Republic of China. Ltd., press equipment for processing 100 tons of product per day, refining, deodorizing, ventilating and packaging equipment for processing 12 tons of oil per day, installed in 2009.

"OR GOLDEN OIL" LLC production enterprise is one of the most prestigious enterprises of our republic for the production of oil products. Businesses that operate competitively in a market economy are rare. Market laws try to squeeze not only manufacturing enterprises, but also trade and service enterprises from the market, because market laws have an objective nature, and regardless of whether it is a legal entity or an individual, it is necessary to settle with the market. Because this is a mandatory condition. It is guaranteed that every manufacturing enterprise will win in the competition if it properly studies the market laws and adjusts its business accordingly.

Personnel employees of the production enterprise "OR GOLDEN OIL" LLC thoroughly study the market rules, determine whether there is a demand for their goods, and then start production. In this way, they prevent the shortage of goods. At present, the company produces 20 different types of vegetable oil products, salstock, meal and other products, and serves to satisfy the demand of the market.

DISCUSSION

The products produced by the enterprise fully meet the requirements of the State standard. Currently, it is very important, because the struggle for quality is the demand of the times.

The production enterprise "OR GOLDEN OIL" LLC mainly has its customers in the domestic market. It can be seen that by now the production enterprise "OR GOLDEN OIL" LLC is making great efforts to increase the volume and range of products.

When analyzing the activity of the production enterprise "OR GOLDEN OIL" LLC, we first of all considered the production activity. In 2019-2021, the company produced oil products in the following amount.

Table 1.

The amount of product production at the production enterprise "OR GOLDEN OIL" LLC, kg.

t/r	Product name	Production, by years			in 2021 compared to 2019, %
		2019	2020	2021	
1	Sunflower oil, refined	1086770	1145519	1217687	112.0
2	Sunflower oil, refined deodorized, frozen	963544	995099	1049063	108.8
3	Safflower oil, refined	96785	101807	133368	137.8
4	Soybean oil, refined	1156273	1328698	1359258	117.6
5	Soapstock	145604	179856	189928	134.4
6	Shot	3783	3986	4206	111.2
	Total	3452789	2754965	3953510	114.5

As can be seen from this table, the production volume was increased in 2019-2021. In 2021, the increase in the production volume of sunflower oil was 112% compared to 2019. The growth of safflower oil production during this period was 137%. Such a situation indicates the

increased attention to Safflower oil. We can confirm that soybean oil production has increased by 117%.

The analysis of the monetary volume of production shows those in tune. The total volume of production in 2021 will be 10,544.1 million soums, which means an increase of 228.6% compared to 2021. Analyzing the composition of production, sunflower oil makes up 31%, soybean oil - 34%, deodorized sunflower oil - 27%.

Table 2.

Amount of product production at the production enterprise "OR GOLDEN OIL" LLC, million soums.

t/r	Product name	Production, by years			in 2021 compared to 2019, %
		2019	2020	2021	
1	Sunflower oil, refined	1226.6	1962.6	2763.4	225.3
2	Sunflower oil, refined deodorized, frozen	984.6	1644.3	2315.9	235.2
3	Safflower oil, refined	150.4	246.6	352.3	234.2
4	Soybean oil, refined	1189.1	1929.3	2717.4	228.5
5	Soapstock	6.4	11.5	16.0	250.0
6	Shot	1047.1	1717.2	2379.1	227.2
	Total	4613.2	7511.5	10544.1	228.6

An important part of the economic analysis is related to the analysis of the efficiency of human resources. Analyzing labor indicators requires looking at the number of employees, labor productivity, and average monthly wages.

Table 3

Dynamics of labor indicators at the production enterprise "OR GOLDEN OIL" LLC.

t/r	Indicators	Unit of measure	Amount by years			in 2021 compared to 2019, %
			2019	2020	2021	
1	The average number of employees on the list	person	36	36	34	94.4
2	Labor productivity	million soums	128.1	208.65	310.1	242.0
3	Labor fund	million soums	111.2	138.4	154.4	138.8
4	Average monthly salary	thousand soums	257.3	320.4	370.5	144.0

As can be seen from the table, the number of employees decreased compared to the plan in the last year, which led to a relative increase in cocktail productivity. At the same time, the growth of labor productivity has been 242% in the last three years, which shows that in the current conditions, the influence of factors other than the labor conditions in the enterprise is strong. The average monthly salary is not sufficiently increased, because the difference between the growth of labor productivity is very large.

The main results of the enterprise's activity are reflected in its financial statements, therefore, the analysis of the balance sheet and financial results of the enterprise is the main task for economists.

In the analysis of financial indicators, we considered the state of the company's balance sheet.

5. - table

Balance indicators of the production enterprise "OR GOLDEN OIL" LLC, by the end of the year, thousand. amount

t/r	Indicators	Amount by years			Change in 2021 compared to 2019, +, -
		2019	2020	2021	
1	Total assets incl	2686121	11043060	11550196	+ 8864075
1.1	Long-term assets	1633957	1462606	1496645	- 137312
1.2	Current assets incl	1052164	9560454	10053551	+ 9001387
	Inventory	605725	2764763	3945290	+ 3339565
	Debtors	446439	614342	65712	- 380727
	Funds	0	6189349	6032549	+ 6032549
2	Total liabilities incl	2686121	11043060	11550196	+ 8864075
2.1	Sources of own funds	977629	2315882	3432867	+ 2455238
2.2	Obligations	1708492	8727178	8117329	+ 6408837

It is known that the assets and liabilities of the 2021 balance sheet are 1,115,019 thousand soums, which is 8,864,075 thousand soums more than the situation at the end of 2019. The increase in assets indicates the rapid growth of the enterprise. This was mainly achieved by the increase of current assets by 9001387 thousand soums. In particular, inventories were increased by 3339565 thousand soums, receivables were reduced by 380727 thousand soums, cash resources were increased by 6032549 thousand soums. The sources of own funds increased mainly due to the increase in undistributed profit, that is, it increased by 2455238 thousand soums. The increase in liabilities by 6,408,837 thousand soums was mainly due to the increase in creditor loans and wages.

General results of product production are shown in table 6.

6. - table

Financial indicators of production enterprise "OR GOLDEN OIL" LLC, mln. amount

t/r	Indicators	Amount by years			in 2021 compared to 2019, %
		2019	2020	2021	
1	Net income from product sales	4613.2	7511.5	10544.1	228.6
2	Cost of goods sold	4015.8	5980.7	7983.2	198.8
3	Gross profit from product sales	597.4	1530.7	2560.9	428.7
4	Main activity benefit	439.8	1239.4	2064.5	469.4

5	Profitability of general economic activity	361.0	1139.8	1509.4	418.1
5	Net profit	105.6	759.0	982.2	930.1

It can be seen that the total figures have increased by 128.6% compared to 2019. The cost of the product has also increased accordingly. Its growth was 98.8%. The financial activities and cost reduction measures carried out in Korokhna are causing a sharp increase in the gross profit of product sales and the profit of the main activity. In the last three years, these indicators have increased by 3.3 times and 3.7 times, respectively.

Table 7

Analysis of the cost of finished products of the OR GOLDEN OIL LLC production enterprise in 2020 by cost.

Expenses	Plan	Real	The difference
Raw materials	4892401	5124680	+ 232279
Fuel and energy	589750	586654	- 3096
Salary and fees	139850	138400	- 1450
Production overheads	63565	63092	- 473
Indirect costs of materials related to production	69320	67923	- 1397
Total cost	5754886	5980749	225863

The actual cost of the products produced in 2020 was 5980749 thousand soums, while the plan indicated 5754886 thousand soums. 225,863 thousand soums were spent more than planned.

Analyzing the cost part of the cost, it can be concluded that 232,279 thousand soums were overspent in the "raw materials and materials" part, which was overspent due to the use of more expensive materials in production compared to the cost calculation. 473,000 soums were saved in the "production overheads" section, which is explained by the absence of costs for current and capital repairs of devices.

If we look at the part of expenses, the output of expenses was observed. For example, 3,096,000 soums were spent due to the increase in the cost of the "Fuel and Energy" section, which is related to the increase in the tariffs of fuel and electricity, which were not taken into account before pricing the product. The cost reduction in the section "Salary and payments" amounted to 1450 thousand soums. This was done in the form of necessary wage payment to workers in situations where the enterprise did not work all day. 1,397,000 soums were saved on "Indirect materials used for production materials".

In 2021, the cost of finished products will be 6784537 thousand soums, according to the plan, it will be 6777255 thousand soums.

Table 8

In 2021, the analysis of the cost of finished products of the production enterprise "OR GOLDEN OIL" LLC

Expenses	Plan	Real	The difference
Raw materials	6777255	6784537	+ 7282
Fuel and energy	902238	896442	- 5796

Salaries and fees	156030	154400	- 1630
Production overheads	75940	75434	- 506
Indirect costs of materials related to production	71277	70349	- 928
Total cost	7982740	7981162	- 1578

As can be seen from the table, 6777255 thousand soums were spent on "Raw materials". This was caused by the increase in the price of agricultural products. 5,796,000 soums were saved in "Fuel and Energy", as a result of which the increase in electricity and gas tariffs was shown.

1,630,000 soums were saved on "Salaries and payments". Only 506,000 soums were saved on "production overhead costs". This is due to unexpected equipment repair costs.

The total economic volume in 2021 was 1578 thousand soums.

CONCLUSIONS

The analysis of the efficiency of the use of resources in the production enterprise "OR GOLDEN OIL" LLC showed that in 2021, the main absolute indicators (income from the sale of products, annual average value of fixed assets, annual average value of working capital, number of employees) increased in the enterprise compared to the previous year. Of these, income from the sale of products, the annual average value of fixed assets, and the decrease in the annual average value of working capital cannot be positively assessed. However, the decrease in the number of employees on the list led to the improvement of a number of indicators of the economic condition of the enterprise, such as labor productivity, profit per employee, armed with funds, working capital with employees.

The products produced by "OR GOLDEN OIL" LLC are intended for wide segments of the population, and their income levels are also taken into account.

In order to improve the activity of the production enterprise "OR GOLDEN OIL" LLC, it is recommended to pay attention to the following areas:

- purchase of agricultural products from legal entities and individuals by money transfer or cash payment, to store, process and sell them for profit;
- receiving and selling any goods not prohibited by the laws of the republic, agricultural processing, from legal entities and individuals in the territory of the republic in exchange for other goods;
- expansion of marketing activities, especially the correct use of marketing principles when selling to foreign countries.

REFERENCES

1. Sh.M. Mirziyoev "New Development Strategy of Uzbekistan" completed second edition, Tashkent "Uzbekistan" publishing house, 2022, 416 p.
2. Sh.M. Mirziyoev "Humanity, goodness and creativity are the foundations of our national idea" Tashkent "TASVIR" publishing house, 2021 y 36 p.
3. The first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A. Karimov "Our main task is to further increase the development of our country and the prosperity of our people" Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2010. 18 p.
4. Abduganiev A., Tolametova Z. Labor capacity of Uzbekistan. T.: "Labor", 1998. 96 p.
5. Under the editorship of K.K. Abdurakhmonov. - T.: Human development. Textbook. i.f.d., prof. "Science and technology", 2013.
6. Derevyagina L.N., Ivashkova N.I. Opit training marketing specialists in the system of additional professional education // Vestnik. 2001
7. Nasirov P. Abdullayeva L. Marketing is the basis of market economy. T.: "Teacher" 2008.
8. Bekmurodov A.Sh., Kosimova M.S., Safarov B.J., Marketing management: Study guide. - T.: TDIU, 2007. - 268 p.
9. Begmatov Sh. A. Kakhorov A.J. Scientific and methodological problems of introducing innovative marketing, "Economics and Education" magazine No. 5, September-October, 2016.
10. Musaeva Sh.A. Usmonova D.I. Innovative marketing: Study guide. - "TURON PUBLISHING" Samarkand 2021.
11. Azimovna M. S., Shokhrukhovich U. F., Sodirovich U. B. Problems in the Implementation of Quality Management Systems in Small Business Enterprises //Eurasian Research Bulletin. – 2022. – T. 7. – C. 54-57.
12. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D. Problems of Marketing in the System of Higher Education //Academic Journal of Digital Economics and Stability. – 2022. – T. 13. – C. 71-75.
13. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D., Shokhrukhovich U. F. INNOVATIVE STRATEGIES OF TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN //EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 1. – C. 1-4.
14. Musayeva S. A., Usmonova D. I., Usmanov F. S. Problems with Marketing Research in the Furniture Market //Eurasian Journal of Academic Research. – 2021.
15. Azimovna M. S., Shokhrukhovich U. F. Development Prospects of Business Subjects in the Republic of Uzbekistan //Web of Scholars: Multidimensional Research Journal. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 4. – C. 13-19.
16. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D., Shokhrukhovich U. F. The Concept of Marketing Policy in Trade and Service Enterprises //CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATIONS ON TOURISM MANAGEMENT AND FINANCE. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 8. – C. 1-5. SCIENCE AND INNOVATION INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL VOLUME 1 ISSUE 5 UIF-2022: 8.2 | ISSN: 2181-3337 105
17. Azimovna M. S., Shokhrukhovich U. F. Ways to expand network marketing and e-commerce in the wholesale of medicines //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876. – 2022. – T. 16. – №. 06. – C. 113-116.

18. Azimovna M. S., Abdurozиковich M. Z. Features of the pharmaceutical market of the Republic of Uzbekistan //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429. – 2022. – T. 11. – №. 06. – C. 201-206.
19. Azimovna M. S., Shohruxhovich U. S. THE ROLE OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS IN THE FOREIGN TRADE TURNOVER OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIIY JURNALI. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 6. – C. 110-112.
20. Azimovna M. S. IMPROVING THE STUDY OF CONSUMER BEHAVIOR //Gospodarka i Innowacje. – 2022. – C. 109-112.
21. Azimovna M. S. et al. Analysis of the main economic and marketing indicators of FE" DAKA-TEX" LLC //ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603. – 2022. – T. 11. – №. 06. – C. 4-7.
22. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D. Optimal principles of assessing the quality of graduates in higher education //Eurasian Scientific Herald. – 2022. – T. 8. – C. 233-238.
23. Azimovna M. S. THE MAIN DIRECTIONS OF THE MARKETING COMPLEX TO INCREASE THE EXPORT POTENTIAL OF PRODUCTS //FORMATION OF PSYCHOLOGY AND PEDAGOGY AS INTERDISCIPLINARY SCIENCES. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 9. – C. 20-23.
24. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D., Shokhruxhovich U. F. WAYS TO USE MARKETING INFORMATION IN THE PROCESS OF EVALUATING THE ENTERPRISE //World Economics and Finance Bulletin. – 2022. – T. 10. – C. 9-12.
25. Azimovna M. S., Shokhruxhovich U. F., Sodirovich U. B. ANALYSIS OF THE MARKET OF TOURIST PRODUCTS OF THE SAMARKAND REGION //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIIY JURNALI. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 4. – C. 422-427.
26. Azimovna M. S., Shokhruxhovich U. F., Rofejon o'g'li R. S. THE PROCEDURE FOR ORGANIZING MARKETING RESEARCH AT INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES IN THE CONTEXT OF MODERNIZATION IN UZBEKISTAN //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI